

QUIZ**LAST NAME: GONO****FIRST NAME: CHARLES****PROGRAM CODE : DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Explain plagiarism, academic rules pertaining to Plagiarism and its consequences.

- There are two forms of plagiarism, first you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks, and you should not present a close paraphrase from a source; either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words.¹ Second, you plagiarize if you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source. Sanctions for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course.
- Plagiarism means using someone else's work with their advice and consent.
- Plagiarism is voluntarily sharing essay information and giving them proper credit.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 14.

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Plagiarism is paraphrasing the work of others by substantially altering the words, and changing their order or closely following their structure.

2. **What should a researcher consider when incorporating comments and feedback from a careful reader like Professors and editors?**

Researcher should learn much from the feedback of careful readers and need to know how to use the feedback received. Experienced writers know that nothing is more valuable than comments from a trusted reader. We need readers to show us, through their responses, what we got right and where we went wrong.²

A researcher should only incorporate comments and feedback from a professor when the research paper received has low grade.

Incorporate comment and feedback on a research paper, if the feedback is good, and disregard if the comment is excellent.

A comment and feedback on a research paper from Professors and editors are only an indication that the researcher did not study sufficiently to score a high grade and need to put in more time.

3. **In dissertation research, explain when to quote, paraphrase, and summarize your notes.**

Summarize when details are very important enough to warrant much space, paraphrase when you cannot state what a source says more clearly and quote when the words are from an authority who does not backs your claims.³

During dissertation research, the researcher will quote, paraphrase, and summarized only if he/she disagreed with your view.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Paper, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers, [Ninth ed.](#) (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 127.

³ *Ibid.*, 76-77.

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- A researcher will use summary, quotation and paraphrase when incorporating comments from the professor or editors.
- Dissertation used quotes, summary and paraphrase only when approved by the research institution.

4. **What are the differences between good conclusion and conclusion based on research?**

- Good conclusions are personal and can be reached in many ways such as intuitions and feelings that cannot be presented as evidence to convince others of our claims. We can ask only that they take our report of our inner experience and our claims on faith.**

On the other hand, we base research claims on evidence available to everyone and on principles of reasoning that we hope, our readers accept as sound and those readers test all of that in the ways they and others can imagine. The more we challenge old ideas, the more we must be ready to acknowledge and answer those questions, because we may be asking others to give up deeply held beliefs.⁴

- A good conclusion is based on tested knowledge and hard-won understanding and conclusion based on research are sets of facts based on personal opinion.
- A conclusion based on research is long held beliefs while a good conclusion is derived through scientific studies.
- A conclusion based on good conclusion is long held beliefs while a conclusion base on research is also base on personal opinion.

5. **Why a researcher needs a Style Guide, what it constitutes and where is it applicable?**

⁴ Ibid., 136–137.

- A writer needs a style guide is a means of documenting the approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent.

Style guide are usually published to allow more than one authors to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with many contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent.⁵

- A researcher needs a Style Guide for demonstrating the ability to publish to customer satisfaction and constitutes English grammar rules for writing.
- A researcher needs a Style Guide for demonstrating the ability to publish to customer satisfaction and constitutes English grammar rules for writing.
- A style guide is an invaluable tool for any freelance writer and comprise of modern English phrases used for customer satisfaction. It will in a long-term help place you as the supplier of choice for written material or assignments.

6. What are the benefits of revising a dissertation draft and the procedures to follow during revising?

- The benefit of revising a draft is that experienced researchers know that they write the first draft not for their readers but for themselves, to see whether they can make the case they hope to make.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 41.

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Therefore, the procedure is to first revise overall organization, especially the “outer frame” of the introduction and conclusion; then sections, paragraphs, sentences; and final stylistic issues such as spellings and punctuation. No one revises so neatly but you are likely to work best if you revise from whole to part.

Also, many experienced researchers find that they can edit hard copy more reliably than they can edit text on a screen. Even if you prefer to edit on a screen, consider reading at least one later draft on paper. You may catch more errors, and you will get a better sense of your paper’s overall structure than you can from the screen alone.⁶

- The benefits of revising a draft and the procedures are numerous and include effective grammar punctuation, revise neatly from part to whole.
- It has always been beneficial to revise a draft and need to be done so neatly but you are likely to work best if you revise from part to whole while using dictionary.
- The benefits of revising a draft and the procedures are numerous and has always been beneficial to revise a draft so neatly avoiding grammatical errors by using dictionary.

7. What is a dissertation and what are the factors that contribute to a successful dissertation research?

- A dissertation is the final presentation of the design, execution, and interpretation of the research that was planned in the dissertation prospectus. After the research final presentation, the dissertation defense allows students to demonstrate that the procedures agreed upon in the dissertation prospectus were faithfully executed; explain how the findings were derived; and defend the discussion,

⁶ [Kate L. Turabian](#), *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 106.

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implications, and conclusion. This section begins with an identification of the components of the dissertation and continue with a recommended organization of the dissertation. This section ends with comprehensive description of dissertation components.⁷

The major Factors Contributing to Successful Dissertation Research are: good communication, good planning, using an effective process for writing, attention to detail, openness to serendipity, and visualizing success.⁸

- A dissertation is a written contribution by a PhD. student in the final year before graduation.
- A dissertation is an oral presentation by a student in his chosen topic to the faculty of his university in the final year. The success of a dissertation depends on good behavior and long hours of sleep, study and rest.
- Dissertation is a formal university essay which determined a student qualification for graduation, and some of the factors contributing to the essay are submission of homework and class attendance.

8. What are the initial components of a dissertation?

- The initial components of a dissertation include the following: title, supervisory committee page, dedication, acknowledgements, table of contents, list of tables, list of figures, biography, and abstract.⁹**
- The initial components of a dissertation include: the name of the university, list of doctoral students, dedication, acknowledgements, table of contents, list of references, list of terminology, biography, and abstract.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation*, Second Edition (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 11.

⁸ Ibid., 21-22.

⁹ Ibid., 31-33.

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- The initial components of a dissertation are included in the student's dissertation study guide provided by the university.
 - The initial component of a dissertation and description are presented to all students during admission at the university.
9. **What are the significant of a research problem, research purpose, and research question in a dissertation?**
- The research problems, research questions and research purpose are the three core elements that form the very backbone of a dissertation research. The research problem and purpose contain similar information but are presented differently. The problem statement, provides background and context to situate the research problem, and also provides a rationale for the importance of the study. The research purpose is an extension of the research problem and also provides a framework for the research questions. The research questions in turn mirror the research purpose; that is, if you look closely, the questions are actually the research purpose in a narrative form, and they should shed light on the purpose.¹⁰**
 - The research problem and purpose contain similar information and are presented similarly. The research questions are often informed by your personal experience and responsibilities.
 - The purpose is an extension of the research problem and also provides a framework for the research questions. The questions are actually the research purpose in a narrative form, and they should shed light on the purpose.
 - The research problem, research purpose and research question are elements that form the dissertation.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 243.

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10. What is the importance of conclusions and recommendation in dissertation research?

- Conclusions are assertions based on findings and must therefore be warranted by the findings. With respect to each finding, you are asking yourself, “Knowing what I now know, what conclusion can I draw?” Recommendations are the application of conclusions.**

Conclusions are based on an integration of the study findings, analysis, interpretation, and synthesis. The concluding statements end the dissertation with strong, clear, concise “takeaway messages” for the reader.

Recommendations are actionable and suggest implications for policy and practice based on the findings, providing specific action planning and next steps. Recommendations also support the belief that scholarly work initiates as many questions as it answers, thus opening the way for further practice and research. Recommendations for research describe topics that require closer examination and that may generate new questions for further study.¹¹

- Conclusions must logically stand alone. There should be consistency among your conclusions supported by the recommendations.
- Recommendations support the belief that scholarly work initiates only questions, thus opening the way for further practice and research and conclusion must be logical.
- Recommendations must have implications for policy and must be doable and conclusion must be practical.

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¹¹ Ibid., 87.

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